

BioValue GAME

Serious Game Development Report

Horizon Europe

Project Name: Biodiversity Value in Spatial Policy and Planning: Leveraging
Multi-level Transformative Change - BioValue

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Executive Summary

"Planning and Acting Towards Biodiversity" is a serious game designed to engage stakeholders in understanding and implementing policy instruments to integrate biodiversity considerations into spatial planning. The game addresses a critical gap: while land-use changes have been pointed among the main causes of BD loss, spatial planning is recognized as fundamental to preventing ecosystem degradation, biodiversity has historically remained disconnected from planning decisions.

The game builds on outputs from the BioValue Horizon Europe project, which identified 44 policy instruments across three perspectives—spatial planning, environmental assessment, and economic-financial tools—for advancing biodiversity in planning contexts. Drawing on a catalogue of 44 instruments derived from the perspectives, and the co-production framework for ecosystem services, the game fosters stakeholder recognition of different policy instruments and their applications, opportunities and trade-offs in implementation, and individual and collective actions needed for biodiversity enhancement

This report describes the game's principles, provides implementation guidance, presents findings from a pilot in Mafra, Portugal, and shares key insights from the process.

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1. Project Context

1.1 Project Details

Project Name: Biodiversity Value in Spatial Policy and Planning: Leveraging Multi-level Transformative Change - BioValue

Grant Agreement Number: 101060790

Project Duration: July 2022 – June 2025 (36 months)

Call Topic: HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01

Project Website: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060790>

1.2 Project description

In Europe, biodiversity strategies have historically focused on habitat protection through spatially segregated and disconnected approaches e sectoral disconnections, which have proven ineffective in addressing the root causes of biodiversity loss. Reports from the OECD and IPBES have identified land use and land cover change as a major direct driver of biodiversity loss, making spatial planning and policymaking central to the challenge. Spatial planning is the backbone of multiple sectoral policies that, either directly or indirectly, drive biodiversity loss through their decisions on infrastructure development and land use patterns. This fragmented approach has created a gap where biodiversity considerations remain disconnected from the spatial planning decisions that fundamentally shape the landscape.

To address this problem, the BioValue project aims to promote transformative change by better integrating biodiversity considerations into spatial planning through three instrumental perspectives (Kørnørv et al., 2024; Laporta et al., 2024; Partidario, 2024; Zhu et al., 2023):

- 1. Spatial Planning and Management Instruments (SP&MI):** Policies, plans, and spatial management approaches that shape land use and development
- 2. Environmental Assessment Instruments (EAI):** Assessment mechanisms and tools for evaluating environmental impacts and biodiversity considerations
- 3. Economic and Financial Instruments (E&FI):** Market-based mechanisms, incentives, and financial tools that can drive biodiversity-positive outcomes

By connecting these instruments across governance levels and recognizing their individual and combined potential for transformative change, BioValue seeks to turn spatial planning from an indirect cause of biodiversity loss into a vehicle for positive

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biodiversity outcomes, moving beyond disconnected habitat protection toward comprehensive, spatially coherent approaches where biodiversity is central to planning decisions.

1.3 Project outputs incorporated in the Game

The game was developed as a follow up of the BioValue final report, *Recommendations for Policy Mixes Combining Instruments from SP&MI, EAI and E&FI across Governance Levels Drawing on their Respective Transformative Potential* (Partidário et al., 2025). This deliverable described the policy instruments that resulted from the work of the different work packages, each following one of the aforementioned instrumental perspectives.

The result was a catalogue of 44 instruments (Table 1) that integrated (i) a spatial planning and policy perspective, drawing on European planning frameworks, ecosystem services approaches, and the mitigation hierarchy; (ii) an environmental assessment perspective, systematizing EIA and SEA practices; and (iii) an economic and financial perspective, examining the role of financial instruments in supporting biodiversity valorisation across the mitigation hierarchy (Kørnørv et al., 2024; Laporta et al., 2024; Partidario, 2024; Zhu et al., 2023).

The set of instruments was further validated and reorganized through a collective process involving discussion among all partners, including stakeholders from the Arenas for Transformation. As a result, the instruments were classified into categories that facilitated their understanding by practitioners and, subsequently, their incorporation into the planning process.

The game adopted a classification by function (Partidário et al., 2025). This classification considered each instrument's role in implementing and shaping policies, influencing behaviour shifts, and ensuring effective implementation and outcomes. The result was six categories that address biodiversity safeguard and enhancement from different angles:

1. **Information:** Improve awareness and knowledge of biodiversity status and safeguards, empowering stakeholders to make informed, biodiversity-conscious decisions.
2. **Planning and Project Design:** Integrate biodiversity considerations directly into spatial development processes, ensuring projects and policies address biodiversity proactively rather than reactively.
3. **Incentive:** Encourage biodiversity-friendly practices through financial or other benefits, rewarding conservation efforts and aligning public and private interests.
4. **Agreement:** Voluntary or negotiated commitments among stakeholders—such as partnerships, conservation contracts, or land-use agreements—that balance development with ecological safeguard.

5. **Regulation:** Legal frameworks establishing mandatory rules and restrictions to ensure long-term biodiversity conservation and sustainable development.
6. **Enforcement:** Mechanisms enabling authorities to ensure compliance and uphold biodiversity commitments, securing land and guaranteeing effective implementation of conservation measures.

Table 1: Catalogue of Instruments classified by instrumental perspective and functional categories

INSTRUMENTS	Instrumental perspective	Classification by Function
Guidelines for Public Space Design and Management: Frameworks for integrating biodiversity into planning and upkeep of public spaces. This can support biodiversity by guiding ecological design in public spaces and favouring integration with green networks.	SP&MI	Information
Best Practice Guidelines for Private Landowners: Recommendations for biodiversity-friendly land management on private properties. This can enhance biodiversity by encouraging more sustainable land management and ecologically friendly practices.	SP&MI	Information
Protected and Conservation Areas Legally designated sites where ecological preservation is prioritised through restrictions on land use and activities. These areas preserve biodiversity by safeguarding habitats, halting land-use change and connecting green spaces.	SP&MI	Planning & Project Design
Land Use Zoning A tool that allocates land (at different scales) for specific uses, balancing development and conservation goals. It supports biodiversity by organising land use to protect habitats and potentially linking natural habitats to increase connectivity.	SP&MI	Planning & Project Design / Regulation
Design-Based Instruments Design approaches incorporating nature-based solutions to support biodiversity. This can enhance biodiversity by prioritising green design and potentially connecting natural habitats.	SP&MI	Planning & Project Design
Land Acquisition The purchase of land by public authorities to protect or restore habitats. It supports biodiversity by preserving natural habitats and improving management for conservation. It can also be used to create green networks.	SP&MI	Planning & Project Design
Density Bonuses Incentives allowing increased building capacity in exchange for biodiversity enhancements, promoting natural elements, habitat preservation, and	SP&MI	Incentives

creation. This can support biodiversity by incentivising habitat safeguard and enhancement.		
Fast-Tracking Approval Process A streamlined approval process for developments that incorporate biodiversity enhancements. This promotes biodiversity by aligning development with ecological goals and reducing delays in projects with positive effects for habitat quality or connectivity.	SP&MI	Incentives
Interim Use Permits for Vacant Land Temporary land-use permits that allow ecological functions on underutilised land. This can improve biodiversity by activating spaces for nature-based solutions and increasing ecological value.	SP&MI	Incentives
Land Rearrangements The reorganisation of land parcel ownership to create larger, ecologically viable habitat patches. This can support biodiversity by creating cohesive, connected habitats. Needs to be paired with conservation areas or zoning for effective biodiversity conservation.	SP&MI	Agreement
Contractualization and Stewardship Programs Voluntary or contractual arrangements where landowners commit to maintaining ecological conditions, ensuring that conservation practices are upheld over time. Habitat quality and connectivity can be enhanced through such collaborative stewardship.	SP&MI	Agreement
Transfer of Development Rights (TDR) Mechanisms that transfer development potential from ecologically sensitive areas to designated growth zones. TDRs can preserve biodiversity by protecting habitats and guiding sustainable development.	SP&MI	Agreement
Performance-Based Approaches (Point Systems) A scoring mechanism that rewards development projects integrating biodiversity-friendly features. They can improve biodiversity by promoting habitat creation and ecological alignment.	SP&MI	Regulation
Quantitative Targets and Standards This regulatory tool sets specific and quantifiable targets for biodiversity conservation in development projects or in land-use planning. They can enhance biodiversity by increasing natural areas and can also improve habitat quality and ecological connectivity.	SP&MI	Regulation
Qualitative and Technological Requirements Regulations setting qualitative ecological and/or technological elements for land use management or infrastructure development projects. They enhance biodiversity by integrating green infrastructure, improving resource management, and promoting good ecological conditions.	SP&MI	Regulation

Compensation Measures Obligations imposed on developers to offset environmental damage through habitat restoration or conservation efforts. These measures can support biodiversity by offsetting impacts and restoring ecosystems.	SP&MI	Regulation
Expropriation of Land and Compulsory Easements A legal tool that allows public authorities to acquire private land or impose usage restrictions for conservation purposes. It helps protect biodiversity by securing land, expanding habitats and/or ensuring better land management.	SP&MI	Enforcement
Administrative Possession This tool allows public authorities to temporarily manage land to address neglect or ecological threats. It can support biodiversity by restoring neglected areas and improving habitat connectivity.	SP&MI	Enforcement
Pre-emption Rights A legal right that allows authorities to purchase land before private buyers to prevent environmentally harmful developments. They help protect ecologically valuable land from development and can support green networks.	SP&MI	Enforcement
Assessment of Cumulative Impacts An evaluation of the aggregated impacts from different planning activities within the same area. Cumulative impact assessments can be an instrument on its own, but assessing cumulative impacts can also be an integrated part of SEAs and EIAs. They capture the broader, systemic interactions that contribute to biodiversity loss or gain, which is essential for understanding how individual impacts can accumulate in time and space.	EAI	Information
Scoping The process of identifying the relevant and significant impacts associated with a given planning activity and which are important to decision making. The issues identified in the scoping process are to be addressed and assessed in the coming SEA and/or EIA. Scoping is conducted early in the EA process and is a crucial step in ensuring that relevant biodiversity impacts are included and assessed.	EAI	Information / Planning & Project Design
Information, Consultation, Engagement Methods for involving stakeholders in biodiversity-related planning decisions. Sharing information and engaging communities collaboratively empowers decision-making, ensuring diverse perspectives are integrated, fostering a more sustainable, biodiversity-focused approach.	EAI	Information
Baseline Assessment Evaluations of biodiversity conditions, challenges, and transformative opportunities to inform land-use decisions. SEA uses existing data to map biodiversity,	EAI	Information

land use, and ecosystem conditions, guiding strategies for habitat restoration and ecosystem connectivity.		
Monitoring and Evaluation Systematic tracking of environmental conditions to assess biodiversity outcomes, refine mitigation measures, and inform future planning cycles and SP&MI through condition indicators, including biodiversity metrics. SEA tracks broader systemic outcomes, like ecosystem health, while EIA focuses on project-specific issues.	EAI	Information / Planning & Project Design
Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) Horizontal instrument and regulation within the EU’s environmental policy framework. SEA integrates biodiversity considerations, along with other critical environmental factors like climatic factors, land and population, at the strategic level of policies, plans and programs.	EAI	Planning & Project Design / Regulation
Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) A horizontal and mandatory instrument aligned with SEA but applied to specific project-levels of planning. EIAs provide a process for the early identification and mitigation of potential impacts to ensure compliance with environmental standards and protect local biodiversity.	EAI	Planning & Project Design / Regulation
Formulation of Alternatives Development of different planning scenarios to evaluate impact on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human well-being. It clarifies trade-offs, supports informed decisions, and prioritises interventions like green infrastructure and habitat connectivity.	EAI	Planning & Project Design
Mitigation Hierarchy A structured approach to minimising environmental damage. It prioritises avoidance, minimisation, reparation, or offsetting through a framework that emphasises harm prevention before considering corrective actions. See Ravn Boess & Kørnøv (2024) for a catalogue of mitigation measures.	EAI	Planning & Project Design / Incentives
Enhancement Measures Proactive efforts to improve current baseline biodiversity conditions beyond mitigation. These measures aim for net-positive environmental outcomes and alignment with biodiversity goals. See Kørnøv et al. (2024b) for a catalogue of enhancement measures.	EAI	Planning & Project Design / Incentives
User Fees and Surcharges Fees or charges for using or consuming goods and services or activities associated with natural areas. They can be used to generate revenue for conservation, recover costs and/or manage demand of land and/or resource use.	E&FI	Incentives
Payments for Ecosystem Services and Direct Payments Voluntary payments (in cash or in kind, including carbon payments) or performance-based compensation for	E&FI	Incentives

undertaking agreed conservation actions to enhance ecosystem services provision or biodiversity conservation.		
Environmental Taxes Levies applied to activities that use ecosystem services or may harm biodiversity and ecosystem services. Success depends on whether relevant authorities have the political power to influence fiscal measures, which are often decided at the state or national level.	E&FI	Incentives
Tax Reliefs and Subsidies: Tax reductions, exemptions, or subsidy payments by the government to support products, technologies, and practices that minimise or prevent environmental degradation or contribute to conservation goals. They are often decided at state or national level.	E&FI	Incentives
Ecological Fiscal Transfers Redistribution of revenues within or between public sector agencies to help lower-tier governments cover costs for providing nature-related public goods and services. Redistribution occurs according to certain environmental criteria, including conservation measures.	E&FI	Incentives
Benefit and Revenue Sharing A flat fee or percentage of public revenues or private income generated from conservation products and services that is shared with local communities to recognise their essential role in conservation and provide incentives and tangible benefits.	E&FI	Incentives
Awards and Recognitions Recognition of individuals, groups, or communities demonstrating good environmental practices to motivate the continuation or improvement of conservation activities. These measures are often combined with other incentives or awareness campaigns.	E&FI	Incentives
Auctions and Tenders Auctions are a mechanism to decide which landowners receive a contract that pays them to change land use and implement conservation measures on their land. Multiple landowners make competing propositions or bids for the price they ask to implement conservation measures, and a buyer – either government or a private entity – selects the best offer.	E&FI	Incentives
Habitat/Mitigation Banking When such a bank is established, a landowner who acts to conserve the natural habitat is seen as making a deposit in the bank and receives credits. Others who want to develop the habitat or otherwise impact on it must purchase a credit from the bank. These instruments are often determined by national law and require high transaction costs for setting up and management.	E&FI	Incentives
Green Products and Eco-Labeling/Certification These initiatives promote income streams from products based on sustainable land and resource use, or provide voluntary trademarks to environmentally sustainable products,	E&FI	Incentives

services, processes or financial products for reaching new markets or generating additional revenues. They aim to provide incentives for businesses to operate in a way compatible with biodiversity conservation.		
Green Credits and Investment Facilities Credit and loans or preferential terms and conditions are granted to green products and enterprises or may stipulate certain environmental requirements in their terms of agreement, including both small-scale loans and large-scale sources of credits and investment for green or biodiversity-based enterprises.	E&FI	Incentives
Quotas and Licenses Quotas that restrict the extraction or use of natural resources can limit environmental damage to sustainable levels. They can be sold or auctioned to generate additional revenue for conservation efforts. Revenues from licenses can also generate additional income for environmental purposes and conservation projects.	E&FI	Incentives
Voluntary Donations and Sponsorships Financial contributions from individuals or companies interested in conservation, or who benefit from ecosystem services, or recognise their role in ecosystem degradation. This also includes voluntarily sponsoring activities that enhance biodiversity or channel funds to local communities.	E&FI	Agreement
Fines, Penalties, and Legal Liabilities Punishments and financial consequences applied to individuals or companies that overuse, harm or pollute the environment. The goal is to avoid or minimise negative environmental impacts or, for damage incurred, to oblige the responsible party legally and financially to compensate for it.	E&FI	Regulation
Deposits and Performance Bonds Individuals or companies undertaking activities which threaten the environment or require some form of mitigation, remediation or management plan are required to make a (usually refundable) deposit of funds against the expenditure involved. This money is earmarked for mitigating or compensating damage.	E&FI	Enforcement

2. Introduction to the game

2.1 Game principles

Serious games are increasingly used in multi-actor settings to promote participatory, collaborative, and learning-based approaches to decision-making. Participants interact and make decisions with consequences grounded in real-world situations, which fosters stakeholder engagement toward a shared objective (Barreteau et al., 2021). Spatial

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planning, understood as a practice that addresses "wicked problems"—situations without a single optimal solution or clear distinction between right and wrong, involving complex interactions among a wide range of stakeholders (Lundström et al., 2016)—has employed games to support scenario development and enhance stakeholder interaction (Sousa, 2026). Given the inherent complexity of planning practice, serious games are recognized as valuable tools for navigating uncertainty while improving communication and deliberation among stakeholders (Mayer et al., 2014).

In this context, the game was developed with the objective of fostering recognition of the different instruments, their opportunities for implementation, potential trade-offs, and the individual actions required to support biodiversity enhancement. To achieve this, the game builds upon the catalogue of instruments and the framework of the co-production of ecosystem services. In this section we will explain the rationale behind the main game features, while specific instructions will be provided in further sections.

The co-production of ES refers to the recognition that ES are produced by the interaction of people and ecosystems (Kachler et al., 2023; Lavorel et al., 2019; Locatelli et al., 2024; Palomo et al., 2016). The framework of capitals has been used to disentangle the co-production (Palomo et al., 2016) into five forms of capital:

- Natural capital: The stock of natural resources that support ecosystems and human well-being
- Human capital: Encompasses health, education, skills, and motivation;
- Social capital: Includes trust, shared values, and networks that facilitate cooperation;
- Physical capital: Comprising physical assets such as infrastructure and tools;
- Financial capital: Composed of the exchange and development of other forms of capital through savings, credit, and investment.

In this game we added also political capital referring to access to power brokers, enabling actors to advance their visions and influence collective action (Emery and Flora, 2006; Jones et al., 2020; Rölfer et al., 2023)

The game had two parts. The first part dedicated to the selection of policy instruments had a collective rationale, where each selected instrument is subject to a debate and requires acceptance from all participants. With this feature, the game simulates the consensus and negotiations behind policy implementation. Complementary to it, the second part is dedicated to the selection of the actions has an individual rationale (Table 2). In this part, the participants expressed what they would do themselves to achieve the objective without putting their decision under the others' consideration. However, players could express their willingness to support actions of others by using collaboration pins, as it will be explained in further sections. In the actions, the participants had the possibility

to link their action to the instruments that were already played, showing how individual agency can support policy implementation.

Table 2: Cards of actions according capital

Capital	Action card
Human	I will change or improve the way I work to help protect and support biodiversity
	I will take part in or support education programs to enhance biodiversity
	I will get certified in my work practices to help enhance biodiversity
Social	I will build partnerships to enhance biodiversity
	I will join a network whose mission is to enhance biodiversity
	I will volunteer in organisations that intervene in green spaces
Financial	I will offer part of my private land for projects that enhance biodiversity
	I will donate resources for initiatives that protect biodiversity
	I will pay fees if they are dedicated to biodiversity conservation
Political	I will organise with like-minded citizens to take action and enhance biodiversity
	I will vote for those who explicitly express their biodiversity projects
	I will publicly contest any action that affects biodiversity enhancement
Physical	I will physically intervene in areas to enhance biodiversity
	I will build infrastructure that helps to enhance biodiversity
	I will use tools and materials that help enhance biodiversity

For the real-case inspiration, a key role was created: the game master. That person has a central role before and during the game. Before the game, the game master contributes to focusing the game: (i) adapting the objective of the game to a context specific central challenge that reflects the enhancement of biodiversity; and (ii) selecting the instruments that best suit the case, out of the total catalogue of instruments. The former task avoids thinking about biodiversity enhancement in a vague and abstract way, while the latter simplifies the game execution, since 44 cards might overwhelm the players with a lot of information. During the game, the game master facilitates the session.

At the start of the game each participant is asked to define an individual and secret objective linked to the central objective. That information remains hidden until the end of the game, the point at which each participant self-reports on a scale from 0 to 10, the satisfaction with the achievement of the individual objective and the satisfaction with the achievement of the game's objective. The combination of both, plus the collaboration received, minus the penalty for the lack of consensus on the instruments they selected, provides the final score for each participant. In this sense, the calculation of the score also reflects trade-offs between individual and collective dimensions.

2.2 Target Audience

The game is designed for anyone involved in a planning process that aims to foster discussion among stakeholders on biodiversity-related issues. It is particularly intended for planning institutions, such as municipal councils, regional and national authorities, scholars, and organizations seeking to strengthen stakeholder engagement in territorial planning processes and build capacity in the application of integrated planning instruments for biodiversity enhancement.

It provides a practical, interactive learning experience that enables participants to explore how spatial planning, environmental assessment, and economic and financial instruments can work together to advance biodiversity objectives while managing competing territorial interests.

3. Game Overview

3.1 Basic Information

Game Title: Planning and Acting Towards Biodiversity

Number of participants: 3 to 8 players

Genre: Strategy

Educational Domain: Spatial Planning and biodiversity

Format: Printable or digital version

Typical Session Length: 2 hours

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Play mode: Multi-player cooperative

Language: Portuguese and English

3.2 Components

3.2.1 Objective Piece

Used to define the main objective of the game, on which all players should focus their efforts.

It is the first piece to be placed by the Game Master in the game area.

3.2.2 Instrument piece

Each Instrument Piece includes its type, such as Inspection, Regulation, or Agreement, the title of the instrument, and the number associated with it.

Instrument Pieces are played in the first two rounds and must be placed adjacent to the Objective Piece and also to one another. They cannot be placed without any adjacent piece.

3.2.3 Action Card

Each Action Card includes a description of the action to be carried out, the action number, and a space for the player to indicate which instrument or instruments the action is linked to. On the back of the card, the player must write how they will carry out the action.

The statement of actions corresponded to examples of actions in five capitals: human, social, financial, physical and political.

Contains detailed information about the instruments and actions in the game, allowing players to consult it whenever necessary.

It also includes a list of examples for possible individual objectives that players may choose to use.

3.3 Instructions

3.3.1 Game adaptation to the context

Before the game, the Game Master needs define the Central Objective of the game according the reality or to a specific problem of the territory over which the game is played. Moreover, the 44 instruments of the catalogue are analysed, and only those that correspond fit into the specific policy frame or planning system of that area are selected. The minimum number of instruments is two per participant.

3.3.2 Game master

The Game Master is the initiator of the game. That person has the motivation to play . During the game, the Game Master is the person who introduces the territory and the central objective, which seeks to respond to existing problems. The Game Master informs participants about the main rules and the dynamics of the session.

The role of the Game Master is to ensure that the game protocol and rules are followed. The Game Master should also moderate the debate and discussion that develops among the participants.

The Game Master guides and clarifies doubts for the participants and controls the time.

3.3.1 Context

Players sit around a table. The number of participants should be between 3 and 8. It is advisable to provide realistic images of the problem, and the map of area.

3.3.2 Materials

Each participant will receive a set of materials:

- 15 predefined Action Cards
- 1 open Action Card
- 1 Individual Card
- 1 Participant Booklet
- 2 Voting Cards

In addition to these components, players will have access to the deck of Instrument Cards when it is their turn to play.

Writing materials should be provided so that players can fill in their respective cards.

3.3.3 Game Dynamics

The game is available in two formats: a digital version and a printable version. These formats support three different settings: (1) in-person using printed materials, (2) in-person using the digital version, and (3) remote using the digital version. As dialogue is fundamental to the game, the remote format requires the game master to create a virtual meeting room on their preferred platform to enable live discussion among participants. The rules are the same across all settings; the following section describes the in-person version using printed materials.

The session begins with the distribution of the materials to each player. Each player fills in their Individual Card with their name and identity, as well as their individual objective, which must remain secret.

The Game Master randomly selects the player who will begin the first round, after which play proceeds clockwise.

The session consists of 3 successive rounds:

- 2 rounds of Planning Instruments;
- 1 round of Actions.

In any round, players may pass their turn, choosing not to present Instrument Cards or Action Cards.

1st and 2nd Rounds: Selection of Instrument Cards

The first player selects, from the set of Planning Instrument Cards, the one they believe best contributes to achieving the Central Objective.

They must explain why they consider this instrument important for achieving the objective and place the hexagonal piece next to the Central Objective.

The remaining participants vote on whether to accept the instrument, placing the Voting Card in front of them with the side facing up that says “Agree” or “Disagree”.

If there is a majority rejection, either by consensus or simple majority, the participant decides whether to take out the card or receive a penalization token.

If there is a majority acceptance, the card remains in play and the session continues.

The game proceeds with the next participant, who receives the deck of instruments, and the process is repeated until the round is completed.

3rd Round: Selection of Action Cards

This round follows a structure similar to the previous ones, but focus on Action Cards, which represent initiatives that players consider relevant for achieving the Central Objective.

Each player may propose up to three Action Cards per round, which must be placed visibly in front of them.

The proposed action could be connected to the instruments already in play, and the player must justify this connection. The number of the associated instruments must be indicated on the Action Card itself.

Closing

After the rounds are completed, players move on to the evaluation and scoring phase, based on the General Objective and the Personal Objective.

Each player must:

- Assign a score from 0 to 10 to their perception of the degree to which the Central Objective has been achieved;
- Assign a score from 0 to 10 to the degree to which their initial Individual Objective has been achieved;
- Indicate the number of:

Penalty tokens

Action Cards proposed;

Collaboration pins

Final Score Calculation

The score for each participant is calculated according to the following formula:

$$RF = A \times B + 2 \times C + 2 \times D - 5 \times E$$

Where:

A = average score for the general objective [0 – 10]

B = average score for the individual objective [0 – 10]

C = number of personal actions

D = number of collaboration pins

E = number of penalty tokens

The -5E part is to penalize players for being unable to negotiate or reach an agreement.

The +2C and +2D parts are meant to reward players' proactivity.

The Game Master collects the results corresponding to the general objective and calculates the average of each participant.

4. Pilot Implementation – Master Plan Revision in Mafra, Portugal

4.1 Context

The printable version of the game was tested in the municipality of Mafra, Portugal. Mafra belongs to the Metropolitan Area of Lisbon and covers 291.66 km² with a population of 76,685 (INE, 2024). Mafra is known for its natural landscapes, which attract visitors from the capital city of Lisbon. Notable attractions include the coastal town of Ericeira and the Tapada Nacional de Mafra, a former royal hunting reserve that provides multiple regulating and cultural ecosystem services.

At the local level, territorial planning instruments — such as the Municipal Master Plan and river management strategies — prioritise key river systems, including the Lizandro and Safarujo rivers, as well as areas that provide cultural ES to local communities. One such area is Serra do Socorro, on the border with the neighbouring municipality of Torres Vedras, which hosts a small chapel and religious sanctuary that attracts visitors from both municipalities, underlining its cultural and recreational significance.

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Figure 1 - Geographical context of Mafra municipality

In 2024, Mafra began the revision of its Municipal Master Plan, the municipality’s main spatial planning instrument. This context provided a favourable opportunity for implementing the game, whose application was initiated at the request of the Head of the Division of Planning and Land Management in May 2025.

The Division issued an open call for participation in the game. The invitation was disseminated through institutional channels and complemented by direct invitations to civic organisations, other municipal divisions, local companies operating in the certification and agriculture sectors, and additional public bodies. The result of the call was 18 confirmed participants (Table 3). With that quorum, it was decided to conduct three games with distinct central objectives.

The context-specific goals selected by the Planning and Land Management Division were:

- **Ecological enhancement of the Atlantic Front:** coastal areas face urban and tourist pressure, coastal erosion, pollution, illegal waste dumping, and invasive species.
- **Enhancement of agriculture in the Lizandro Valley:** areas that face landscape and soil degradation, illegal occupation, tourist and urban pressure, motorised sports, eucalyptus monoculture, invasive species, and illegal waste dumping.
- **Ecological enhancement of Serra do Socorro:** the area faces landscape and soil degradation, illegal occupation, tourist and urban pressure, eucalyptus monoculture, invasive species, and illegal waste dumping, which damage natural habitats, reduce biodiversity, and weaken the quality of the landscape.

The 20 policy-instrument cards selected to pursue these goals were: Best Practice Guidelines for Private Landowners; Information, Consultation, Engagement; Monitoring and Evaluation; Fast-Tracking Approval; Habitat/Mitigation Banking; Tax Reliefs and Subsidies; Green Credits and Investment; Green Products and Eco- Labelling/Certification; Payments for Ecosystem Services and Direct Payments; Enhancement Measures; Fines, Penalties, and Legal Liabilities; Environmental Taxes; Land Use Zoning; Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA); Protected and Conservation Areas; Land Acquisition; Expropriation of Land and Compulsory Easements; Contractualization and Stewardship Programs; and Land Rearrangements.

Table 2 – Players according their type

Descriptor	Description	Number of participants
Division of Environment – Municipal Council	Practitioners from the technical component of the public actor	2
Division of Archaeology – Municipal Council	Practitioners from the technical component of the public actor	1
Division of Urban Rehabilitation – Municipal Council	Practitioners from the technical component of the public actor	1
Division of Tourism – Municipal Council	Practitioners from the technical component of the public actor	1
Division of Planning and Land Management – Municipal Council	Practitioners from the technical component of the public actor	2
Division of Urbanism – Municipal Council	Practitioners from the technical component of the public actor	1
President of Milharado Parish	Executive actor of public actor from the sub-local scale	1
Biosphere Portugal	Sustainability certification company	3
Quinta do Arneiro	Family business of organic farming	1
Hanzwine	Winery company	1

Plata Floresta	Environmental organisation focused on forest regeneration	1
ICEA	Association dedicated to culture, research, and education	1
A2S	Leader Local Action Group – Public-private association in the farming sector	1
Citizen	Individual citizen without declared affiliation	1

4.2 Game application

The printed materials were displayed at each table before players arrived. Once seated, the game master explained the setting's context and demonstrated how to initiate play. Players easily followed the instructions, suggesting that the game's introductory mechanics were accessible.

All 20 instrument cards were activated across the three roundtables, indicating broad engagement with the full set of cards. However, card selection varied by table: Best Practice Guidelines for Private Landowners, Information Consultation Engagement, and Enhancement Measures appeared most frequently, while other instruments saw limited play. This variation reflects how players prioritised instruments in response to each table's Central Objective rather than treating all cards as equally relevant.

In the second round, some players passed their turn because the card they wanted to play had already been selected by another participant. Players generally showed a tendency to seek acceptability for their instrument choices, resulting in few utilisations of penalty tokens. This suggests that the consensus mechanism—requiring collective agreement before cards enter play—effectively prompted negotiation and compromise among participants.

In the round of the actions, players showed a tendency to place multiple cards simultaneously, taking advantage of the unlimited-selection rule for this round. Those placing around many cards provided less detailed information about how each action would be performed, while players selecting fewer cards offered richer context and specificity. Most players opted for pre-designed action cards rather than blank cards. However, some players noted difficulty distinguishing between certain cards, as their statements were perceived as similar, pointing to a potential refinement in card language or visual differentiation.

Selection of actions concentrated in two areas: physical interventions (I will use tools and materials that help enhance biodiversity) and capacity-building (I will take part in or support education programs to enhance biodiversity). This clustering demonstrates that players gravitated toward tangible and knowledge-transfer mechanisms within the game scenario.

Collaboration pins revealed which actions players perceived as synergistic: "I will take part in or support education programs to enhance biodiversity" and "I will build partnerships to enhance biodiversity" received the most pins. This pattern suggests that actions framed around relational processes fostered stronger perceived collective benefit than individually-oriented interventions. However, a design limitation emerged: collaboration pins were only visible to those who received them. Players who gave pins had no visual confirmation of their contribution, and the connection between giver and receiver was not represented in the game space. This asymmetry reduced the mechanic's potential to reward collaborative intention or visibility of collective commitment.

The closing phase differed across tables. At some tables, players remained engaged through to the end and expressed enthusiasm about determining the winner. At others, players showed limited interest in the scoring system and instead focused on the conversations the game had triggered.

A satisfaction survey administered after gameplay showed that the majority of participants found the game easy to follow and appreciated it as an engaging way to explore complex topics. This positive reception held across all three table settings.

Figure 1: At the left, picture of the first part, showing a penalty pin, and at the right, picture of the second part, showing collaboration pin

5. Key insights

The implementation of the game proved to be successful in engaging stakeholders towards collective and individual decisions on biodiversity in the context of planning. Here are some of the main insights from the application:

Interaction is fundamental, regardless of format

The digital version of the game contributes to its dissemination, facilitating implementation without printed materials. However, this does not replace live dialogue. In the pilot in Mafra, together with the pre-testing sessions organized among the game developers, we found that interaction proved fundamental. The debates and possible collaborations benefited from dialogue mediated by the game master.

Cards help introduce planning instruments

Based on previous interactions with the instrument catalogue, the card version showed greater engagement. The creation of a single piece containing the instrument name and category, supported by the booklet with extended definitions, allowed for better review and comparison among instruments. Moreover, using different colors for each category facilitated understanding and application.

Communicating the game objective is sufficient to guide the session

Revealing the scoring system before the game starts can modify participants' behavior to pursue a higher score. Since this is a serious game—where the goal is to simulate a real-world situation and act accordingly—it is acceptable not to provide details about winning conditions, but rather to communicate the objective. With that information, players maintain focus, have sufficient information to make decisions, and do not alter their selections according to a strategy to win.

We encourage future users to share their insights and suggestions for improvement by contacting us at: citua@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

6 Digital Version

We developed a multiplayer digital version of the BioValue game using Unity and the Photon library. The game needs local installation and is opensource (check the resources and materials section). A digital session is started by a game master that sets the parameters of the game to play and invites players to join, in their own computer. This version works similarly to the tabletop version using the same mechanics and cards.

7. Resources and Materials

Game Download: <https://oppla.eu/biovalue/biovalue-resources>

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Source Code: <https://github.com/GAIPS/BioValueGame>

8. Dissemination

The game process and its results in the use case were presented in the following international conferences:

Baptista e Silva, J., Loupa-Ramos, I., David, N. *Gaming Towards Biodiversity: Insights from Serious Games in The Planning Context*. Proceeding to World Planning Conference, Helsinki, Finland, June, 2026.

Hoyos-Rojas, L.; Inostroza, L.; Loupa-Ramos, I. *Joining Forces: Stakeholder Contributions to Ecosystem Services in Spatial Planning*. Proceeding to Ecosystem Services Conference, Prague, Czech Republic, May, 2026.

Hoyos-Rojas, L.; Inostroza, L.; Loupa-Ramos, I. *Joining Forces: Stakeholders' Agency for Biodiversity: Ecosystem Services Governance in the Planning Context*. Proceeding to World Planning Conference, Helsinki, Finland, June, 2026.

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